

APPENDIX C

Collaborative problem-solving skill matrix PISA

Table C.1

CPS Framework PISA 2015 (OECD, 2013)

	1. Establishing and maintaining shared understanding	2. Taking appropriate action to solve the problem	3. Establishing and maintaining team organisation
A. Exploring and Understanding	(A1) Discovering perspectives and abilities of team members	(A2) Discovering the type of collaborative interaction to solve the problem, along with goals	(A3) Understanding roles to solve problem
B. Representing and Formulating	(B1) Building a shared representation and negotiating the meaning of the problem (common ground)	(B2) Identifying and describing tasks to be completed	(B3) Describe roles and team organisation (communication protocol/rules of engagement)
C. Planning and Executing	(C1) Communicating with team members about the actions to be/ being performed	(C2) Enacting plans	(C3) Following rules of engagement, (e.g., prompting other team members to perform their tasks.)
D. Monitoring and Reflecting	(D1) Monitoring and repairing the shared understanding	(D2) Monitoring results of actions and evaluating success in solving the problem	(D3) Monitoring, providing feedback and adapting the team organisation and roles